

An Environmentally Adaptive System for Rapid Acoustic Transmission Loss Prediction

Gordon Wichern, Mahmood R. Azimi-Sadjadi, and Michael Mungiole

Abstract—An environmentally adaptive system for prediction of acoustic transmission loss (TL) in the atmosphere is developed in this paper. This system uses expert neural network predictors, each corresponding to a specific environmental condition. The outputs of the expert predictors are combined using a fuzzy confidence measure and a non-linear fusion system. Using this prediction methodology the computational intractability of traditional acoustic models is eliminated. The proposed system is tested on a synthetic acoustic data set for a wide range of geometric, source, and environmental conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Prediction of acoustic transmission loss (TL) in the atmosphere has become increasingly important in recent years. The TL at a given location depends on a variety of factors, namely problem geometry, source frequency, characteristics of the ground surface, refraction caused by wind and temperature conditions, and atmospheric turbulence. Several methods exist to accurately predict TL values in atmospheric acoustic propagation, but the computation times are generally excessive for situations when near real-time environmental awareness is desired. With the increasing importance of Unattended Ground Sensor (UGS) technologies [1] in localizing and tracking acoustic sources, the need for real-time awareness of acoustic propagation effects has recently emerged.

The problem of fast and accurate TL prediction can be addressed using artificial neural networks [2]. In our application neural network predictors are trained to capture a mapping function from the input parameter space used to describe the propagation problem of interest, to the output space of TL values. From the results presented in [2] it was shown that a single neural network predictor lost accuracy at high frequencies, large values of horizontal separation between acoustic source and receiver, and several important atmospheric and ground conditions. In order to overcome these limitations, we propose a method where a different non-linear prediction model is estimated for data corresponding to a specific environmental condition, thus generating a bank of expert non-linear predictors. This creates an environmentally adaptive TL prediction scheme, which exploits a decision making system for selecting the appropriate predictors under a given condition. The decision making system works by assigning a fuzzy confidence (weighting) measure to the

predicted output of each predictor in the bank. A fusion system is then used to optimally combine the weighted estimates from the different predictors in the bank, obtaining a near real-time TL estimate.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a review of the parabolic equation model for sound propagation in the atmosphere. Section III describes the proposed TL prediction system. Test results and discussions of the environmentally adaptive system are provided in Section IV. Finally, Section V provides conclusions and suggestions for future work.

II. REVIEW OF THE PARABOLIC EQUATION MODEL FOR SOUND PROPAGATION

Due to the non-stationary behavior of the physical atmosphere, as well as the fact that no actual field data set encompasses the variability and randomness required for the large range of parameters used to describe our propagation environment, our data set was synthetically generated using a non-dimensional parabolic equation (PE) model. Part of the rationale for using the non-dimensional PE model is that it reduces the number of parameters required to specify the propagation environment from 15 or more, to the 10 non-dimensional neural network input parameters discussed in [2]. We know from Bellman's curse of dimensionality [3] that function approximation methods tend to be less accurate as the dimension of the input space increases, and the non-dimensional PE model helps to overcome these effects.

The crux of our model as described in [4] is the two-dimensional narrow-angle PE, which approximates the full wave equation for atmospheric sound propagation by

$$\frac{\partial P(x, z)}{\partial x} = \frac{j}{(2k_0)} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} + k_{eff}^2(z) - k_0^2 \right) P(x, z). \quad (1)$$

where x and z are the horizontal and vertical coordinates, respectively of the sound pressure field in the propagation direction. The reference value of the wave number is denoted by k_0 and defined by $k_0 = 2\pi f/c_0$ where f is the frequency and c_0 is the reference sound speed. We define the effective wavenumber as $k_{eff}(z) = 2\pi f/c_{eff}(z) + j\nu(z)$ where ν is an attenuation coefficient modeling the absorption of sound energy as the acoustic wave propagates higher in the atmosphere [5], and c_{eff} is the effective sound speed [6] defined as the speed of sound plus the wind speed component in the propagation direction. The variable $P(x, z)$ represents a substitute for the actual sound pressure $p(x, z)$ at point (x, z) . The actual sound pressure can be obtained from the relation $p(x, z) = P(x, z)exp(jk_0x)\sqrt{x}$. This relation is necessary

Gordon Wichern and Mahmood R. Azimi-Sadjadi are with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, CO 80523-1373, USA. E-mail: azimi@engr.colostate.edu

Michael Mungiole is with the Army Research Laboratory, Adelphi, MD 20783-1197, USA. E-mail: mmungiole@arl.army.mil

because of the cylindrically symmetric 2-D approximation used in the derivation of (1) as discussed in [4].

If we use frequency f , reference sound speed c_0 , and reference air density ρ_0 to define the dimensionless quantities: $\bar{p} = p/(\rho_0 c_0^2)$, $\bar{P} = P\sqrt{(c_0/f)/(\rho_0 c_0^2)}$, $\bar{x} = xf/c_0$, $\bar{z} = zf/c_0$, $\bar{k}_{eff} = k_{eff}c_0/f$, and $\bar{k}_0 = k_0c_0/f = 2\pi$, we can [2] write the non-dimensional version of (1) as,

$$\frac{\partial \bar{P}(\bar{x}, \bar{z})}{\partial \bar{x}} = \frac{j}{(4\pi)} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \bar{z}^2} + \bar{k}_{eff}^2(\bar{z}) - 4\pi^2 \right) \bar{P}(\bar{x}, \bar{z}) \quad (2)$$

where the overbars indicate dimensionless variables.

To compute the acoustic field the PE model uses a spatial marching procedure where the sound field is calculated at discrete range steps along the propagation path [4]. This allows the calculated acoustic field at any given point to incorporate reflection and refraction effects that occurred previously along the propagation path. Additionally, because more refraction is present at high frequencies the step size in the spatial marching procedure is inversely proportional to the source frequency. At low frequencies and small horizontal separations between source and receiver the PE model can compute TL values rather quickly. However, as frequency and horizontal separations increase the computation time increases dramatically. Furthermore, most acoustic sources of interest contain several different frequency components and require TL calculations at several frequencies making the PE model method intractable in these types of situations. It is for these reasons that we use neural network predictors to approximate the PE model and overcome the computational requirements inherent in the PE model.

The location of the acoustic receiver where the TL is computed can be defined as (\bar{x}_c, \bar{z}_r) , where \bar{x}_c is the non-dimensional horizontal separation between source and receiver and \bar{z}_r is the non-dimensional receiver height. The sound pressure level (SPL) in decibels (dB) at receiver location (\bar{x}_c, \bar{z}_r) can be determined from the following equation [5]

$$SPL = 20 \log_{10} |\bar{p}(\bar{x}_c, \bar{z}_r)| \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{p}(\bar{x}_c, \bar{z}_r) = \bar{P}(\bar{x}_c, \bar{z}_r) \exp(j2\pi\bar{x}_c)/\sqrt{\bar{x}_c}$ is the actual non-dimensional sound pressure. Since we are interested in predicting the amount of acoustic attenuation from source to receiver, we will refer to SPL diminishment from source to receiver as transmission loss (TL) [2] throughout this paper. The value output by the PE model using (3), will be used as the target value (label) for the developed neural network-based prediction systems.

A. Ground Profile

The model used for the ground surface in the PE model will have a large impact on the calculated TL values, because the ground surface causes wave reflections that interact with the direct acoustic wave as it propagates away from the source. In our formulation, \bar{Z}_c denotes the non-dimensional ground impedance using the model described in [7] and given by,

$$\bar{Z}_c = \bar{q} \left[\left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{(1 - j\pi N_{pr} \bar{q}^2 / \bar{\sigma})^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1 - j\pi \bar{q}^2 / \bar{\sigma})^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

where N_{pr} and γ are the Prandtl Number and the ratio of specific heats for air respectively. The non-dimensional static flow resistivity $\bar{\sigma}$, is defined by $\bar{\sigma} = \sigma s_p^2 / (f \rho_0 \Omega)$, where s_p is the pore shape factor, and Ω is the porosity [8]. The tortuosity [8] to porosity ratio \bar{q} is defined as $\bar{q} = q/\Omega$, where q is the tortuosity.

The static flow resistivity σ models the hardness of the ground surface with high values corresponding to hard ground (i.e. asphalt) and low values corresponding to soft ground (i.e. fresh snow). The porosity Ω models the number of pores in the ground surface, and the tortuosity q models the twisting of the pores, with $q = 1$ representing vertical alignment with the ground surface and $q > 1$ representing twisted pores.

B. Atmospheric Profile

Refraction, or the bending of sound waves in the near ground atmosphere due to vertical gradients in wind and temperature is an important factor in acoustic modeling. With temperature and wind directly related to the speed of sound, we can include atmospheric refraction effects in the sound speed profile of the PE model. Different atmospheric profiles can cause sound to refract in different directions, and hence cause hot spots and shadow regions to appear in different locations of the sound field. We now discuss the atmospheric profiles used for the non-dimensional PE model.

The atmospheric profiles in the near ground atmosphere, used in our study, fall from the equation for the effective sound speed [6]

$$c_{eff}(z) = c(z) + u(z) \cos \beta \quad (5)$$

where u is the wind component in the horizontal direction, β is the azimuthal angle (angle between the sound propagation and wind directions), and c is the actual sound speed in air described by

$$c(z) = c_0 \left(1 + \frac{T'(z)}{2T_0} \right) \quad (6)$$

It is assumed, for this formulation of the sound speed c , that the effect of humidity is small and hence negligible. Here, T' symbolizes the quantity of a small temperature variation about the ambient value T_0 . The near ground temperature T and wind velocity u profiles are formed using the Monin-Obukhov similarity theory [9], and derived in [2]. From (5) and (6) we see that the wind and temperature profiles used essentially describe the effective sound speed as a function of height. The ratio of adiabatic coefficients for sound speed and wind will be denoted by A and, is described in [6]. In our data set A equals the temperature dependent

sound speed scale, c_* , divided by the wind dependent friction velocity, u_* . This ratio is extremely important in governing the direction of sound refraction in the atmosphere, and illustrates the relative contributions of wind and temperature gradients in the acoustic atmosphere as they relate to sound refraction. Typically, values of $A > 0$ occur during calm nighttime conditions, and cause sound to refract downward. Values of $A < 0$ tend to occur when the sun heats the ground during the daytime and cause sound to be refracted upward.

C. Model Parameters as Inputs to TL Predictors

As our ultimate goal is to approximate the acoustic propagation solution of the PE model using neural networks for improved prediction speed, we must define a parameter set to be used as neural network inputs. We now discuss the 10 parameters that are used as neural network inputs, and also specify the acoustic environment simulated by the PE model. To select the range of these individual input parameters, we choose values that cover the entire range of atmospheric and ground conditions likely to be encountered in practice, as well as frequency and geometric ranges that are of tactical importance in battlefield environments.

Table I provides the range of values used in our study as well as the baseline and extreme values for each input parameter. The baseline value is a value that is likely to be encountered in practice, and often near the middle of the range for each parameter. The extreme values were usually near one end of the range for a selected parameter, and will be used later to examine the robustness of the developed prediction schemes. A detailed discussion on the selected range for each parameter of Table I can be found in [2].

The non-dimensional PE model just described will be used to create a data set, which will subsequently be used to train neural network predictors to capture the input-output mapping between the input parameters used to describe the PE model and the TL value generated by the PE model. The neural network input data is defined using the 10 parameters from Table I as $\mathbf{x} = [f, \bar{x}_c, \bar{z}_s, \bar{z}_r, \beta, \bar{u}_*, \bar{c}_*, \bar{\sigma}, \bar{q}, \bar{z}_0]^T$, where each component of \mathbf{x} is varied independently and uniformly over its specified range. The value output by the PE model from (3) is defined as y , and is the target value used in neural network training. Using the non-dimensional PE model, a data set of $N=40,163$ pairs $\{\mathbf{x}_j, y_j\}_{j=1}^N$, were generated for neural network training. Once trained, our neural network-based predictors will be able to accurately approximate the PE model at all geometric, atmospheric, and ground conditions of interest over a range of frequencies without the high computational cost inherent in the PE model.

III. AN ENVIRONMENTALLY ADAPTIVE TL PREDICTION SYSTEM

Figure 1 shows the block diagram of the environmentally adaptive TL prediction scheme proposed in this paper. In Figure 1 \mathbf{x}_j represents the j th input vector, \hat{y}_{ij} is the estimate from the i th predictor in the bank, C_{ij} is the confidence measure given to the i th predictor in the bank, and \hat{y}_{TLj} is the final output of the system. The environmentally adaptive

system provides improved acoustic TL prediction when compared to a single neural network, which cannot accurately handle the drastic environmental changes caused by the high variability of included input parameters in the PE model data sets. This structure also provides the flexibility to modify the prediction system if new environmental conditions are encountered, while providing the ability to fine tune the system for increased accuracy under conditions of interest.

Each back-propagation neural network (BPNN) predictor in Figure 1 is trained for a specific environmental condition, which corresponds to a specific combination of selected input parameters. The prediction results of these BPNNs are given a fuzzy confidence measure (close to one for the most appropriate predictor, or close to zero for the least appropriate), and then combined using another BPNN in the fusion center. It is envisaged that this mixture of environmentally specific experts will improve overall acoustic TL prediction accuracy using the principle of divide and conquer [3].

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the environmentally adaptive TL prediction system

A. Environmentally Specific Data Subsets

In order to create expert networks for specific environmental conditions we must first partition the data into environmentally specific data sets. Traditionally, an unsupervised learning technique, e.g., clustering [10] is used to partition input data into various subsets. In our application we have prior knowledge of the physical mechanisms responsible for the variation in TL values output by the PE model in different regions of the input space. Since this knowledge is available, we will use it to partition the data into environmentally specific subsets as opposed to an unsupervised learning algorithm. An environmentally specific data set can be described as a subset of data where all cases correspond to a certain environmental condition, e.g., soft ground (low σ) or high wind conditions (high u_*).

The number of environmentally specific data subsets will be signified by M . These environmentally specific data subsets denoted by $D_i, i = 1, \dots, M$ correspond to specific

TABLE I
RANGE AND BASELINE VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS USED TO SPECIFY THE PE MODEL DATA SET OF OUR STUDY.

Parameter (units)	Non-dimensional definition	min	max	baseline	extreme
Frequency (Hz)	f	20	200	50	200
Horizontal separation (m)	$\bar{x}_c = x_c f / c_0$	100	900	500	900
Source height (m)	$\bar{z}_s = z_s f / c_0$	0	5	0	5
Receiver height (m)	$\bar{z}_r = z_r f / c_0$	0	5	0	5
Azimuthal angle (rad)	β	0	π	0	π
Friction velocity (m/s)	$\bar{u}_* = u_* / c_0$	0.05	0.5	0.28	0.067
Sound-speed scale (m/s)	$\bar{c}_* = c_* / c_0$	-1.18	0.1	-0.2	-1.11
Static flow resistivity (Pa·s/m)×10 ⁶	$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma s_p^2 / (f \rho_0 \Omega)$	0.025	2	0.2	1
Tortuosity/porosity	$\bar{q} = q / \Omega$	1.54	10	2.8	7.5
Roughness length (m)	$\bar{z}_0 = z_0 g / c_0^2$	0.001	0.1	0.01	0.01

environmental conditions from the data set (i.e., high c_* values, low u_* values, etc.). The D_i have soft membership meaning that a given input sample \mathbf{x}_j can belong to multiple environmentally specific data subsets (e.g. sample \mathbf{x}_j can have a low c_* value and a high u_* value).

For the PE model data we partition the training and validation sets into six environmentally specific data subsets ($M=6$). We chose six data subsets, because using fewer would not allow significant partitioning and the prediction scheme would exhibit behavior similar to a single BPNN. If more than six environmentally specific data subsets were used there would not have been sufficient data to train predictors for all conditions of interest. Another factor to be considered when partitioning the data is the inclusion of overlap between environmentally specific data subsets. Having samples belong to multiple environmentally specific data subsets allows multiple experts to collaborate in estimating the output TL.

For the presented data partitioning method, the parameters chosen to divide the original data set were the friction velocity u_* , and the sound speed fluctuation scale c_* . These parameters were chosen because the results in [2] showed that they are environmental parameters with a significant influence on the TL, and also responsible for increased neural network output errors as they were varied over their respective ranges. The combination of c_* (temperature) and u_* (wind) govern the direction sound waves are refracted as they propagate higher in the atmosphere. Thus, each partitioned data subset can be thought of as corresponding to different atmospheric refraction conditions. Note that other important parameters such as the frequency, f , and the horizontal separation between source and receiver, x_c , were not chosen as they are dependent on the source of interest and not the environment.

The six environmentally specific conditions used in the first partitioning method are as follows:

- 1) High values of u_* ($u_* \geq 0.275m/s$).
- 2) High values of c_* ($c_* \geq 0m/s$).
- 3) Moderate values of u_* ($0.125m/s < u_* < 0.425m/s$).
- 4) Moderate values of c_* ($c_* \geq -0.9m/s$).
- 5) Low values of u_* ($u_* < 0.275m/s$).
- 6) Low values of c_* ($c_* < -0.3m/s$).

The high, medium, and low u_* data subsets were chosen to divide the entire range of u_* into roughly equal thirds with significant portions of overlap. The high c_* subset ($c_* > 0$)

was chosen because it corresponds to the stable atmospheric regime and downward refraction conditions, where the PE model behavior is highly variable as a function of c_* . The medium and low c_* data subsets were chosen to partition the entire range of c_* into approximately equal halves with significant portions of overlap. Once these environmentally specific data subsets are partitioned, they are used to train the environmentally specific predictors shown in Figure 1.

B. Environmentally Specific BPNN Predictors

In order to train the environmentally specific BPNN predictors of Figure 1 on the partitioned data subsets we must first choose network structures and a training algorithm. We used a two-layer, or one hidden layer BPNN with 45 neurons in the hidden layer, which was determined to be an effective network structure in [2], along with the Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm [11]. The networks used for TL prediction have 10 inputs (the 10 dimensional feature vector \mathbf{x}_j), and a single output (the estimated TL \hat{y}_j). We will refer to this as a 10-45-1 BPNN structure. The output layer had a linear activation function, which is standard for regression problems, because of the wide range of possible output values. Before training the BPNN we sub-divide our PE model data sets into thirds forming training, validation, and testing sets. The purpose of the training set is to estimate the BPNN parameters used to capture the non-linear mapping function. We use 10 different parameter initializations for a given BPNN, and the initialization that performs best on the validation set is chosen and saved for further study, hence providing us a BPNN with good generalization capability. The testing set is used for thorough performance evaluation of the trained BPNN on data it has never seen before. While the testing set is the same for each environmentally specific predictor in Figure 1, the training and validation sets are different for each expert predictor, i.e., only those samples belonging to the appropriate environmentally specific data subset are used.

A two-layer network structure worked well for the expert predictors corresponding to all environmentally specific data subsets except the one used with the $c_* > 0$ subset, which required a three-layer (10-22-11-1) BPNN to obtain acceptable TL predictions. Thus, two-layer BPNN predictors were used for all of the environmentally specific experts of Figure 1 except the one corresponding to the $c_* > 0$ subset. Once trained each environmentally specific BPNN will be

used to predict the TL for a given combination of input parameters. The output of the i th environmentally specific BPNN predictor for the j th input parameter vector will be denoted by \hat{y}_{ij} . The decision making system used to select the most appropriate environmentally specific predictors for a given input vector will be described in the next section.

C. Confidence Measure Assignment

The assignment of the confidence measure weights is done independently of the training of environmentally specific predictors and the fusion center. The purpose of the confidence measure component of Figure 1 is to assign confidence weights to the output of each environmentally specific predictor, depending on the employed partitioning method and the value of the input parameter vector, \mathbf{x}_j . In order to calculate these confidence measure weights we used fuzzy set theory [12], which provides a convenient method to determine how appropriate each environmentally specific predictor is for a given input vector. Fuzzy sets allow natural language terms such as high, medium, and low to be represented mathematically, by allowing elements to be partial members of different sets with varying degrees of membership at the same time [13].

Fuzzy measures are conceptually different from probabilities as they do not measure the relative frequency that a certain event occurs or the likelihood of an event, but rather a degree of membership in a given set. We now provide definitions for a *fuzzy set* and a *fuzzy variable*. A fuzzy set [13] F in a universe of discourse U is characterized by its membership function $\mu_F(\cdot) : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$, which maps each element of U to a real number in the interval $[0, 1]$. A fuzzy set F in U may also be considered as a set of ordered pairs [14] consisting of an element u and its corresponding membership function value, i.e. $\{(u, \mu_F(u)) | u \in U\}$. A fuzzy variable [13] V_z is described by a 4-tuple: $\{z, T(z), \chi, M(z)\}$ where z is the symbolic name or linguistic variable, $T(z) = \{T_z^1, T_z^2, \dots, T_z^L\}$ is the set of linguistic labels associated with z , χ is a closed interval of real numbers containing the range of values over which $T(z)$ is defined, and $M(z) = \{M_z^1, M_z^2, \dots, M_z^L\}$ is a semantic rule function that returns the meaning of a given linguistic label in terms of its membership function. That is T_z^ℓ , $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, L$ is a linguistic label associated with membership function M_z^ℓ , $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, L$. For example if linguistic variable z represents wind speed, then $T(z)$ might be $\{\text{slow, medium, fast}\}$, χ may be $[0, 100]$ (miles per hour), and $M(z)$ represents the membership functions assigned to each element in $T(z)$.

Given the j th input vector denoted by \mathbf{x}_j , and its predicted output value from the i th predictor in the bank \hat{y}_{ij} , our goal is to assign a confidence measure C_{ij} to \hat{y}_{ij} . The confidence measure C_{ij} is assigned to each predicted output \hat{y}_{ij} , based upon the degree of membership that input sample \mathbf{x}_j belongs to the i th environmentally specific data set, D_i . This is done by defining a fuzzy variable for each input parameter that is used to partition the input data into environmentally specific subsets following the procedure of Section III-A. We define

K as the number of parameters used to partition the data into environmentally specific subsets. For example, in the presented data partitioning method, one fuzzy variable will correspond to c_* , a second fuzzy variable will correspond to u_* , and thus $K = 2$. If we let z_k denote the k th parameter used to partition the data (i.e. c_* or u_* , in this case) we define the fuzzy variables V_{z_k} , as

$$V_{z_k} = \{z_k, \{T_{z_k}^1, T_{z_k}^2, \dots, T_{z_k}^{L_k}\}, \chi_k, \{M_{z_k}^1, M_{z_k}^2, \dots, M_{z_k}^{L_k}\}\},$$

for $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ (7)

where χ_k is the range of real numbers associated with z_k , $T_{z_k}^{\ell_k}$, $\ell_k = 1, 2, \dots, L_k$ is the linguistic label associated with membership function $M_{z_k}^{\ell_k}$, and L_k is the number of fuzzy sets affiliated with z_k . For the j th input vector \mathbf{x}_j the value of the k th partitioning parameter $z_k(j)$, is mapped to the fuzzy set labeled by $T_{z_k}^1$ with membership degree $M_{z_k}^1(z_k(j))$ and to the fuzzy set labeled by $T_{z_k}^2$ with membership degree $M_{z_k}^2(z_k(j))$, and so on. For example, in the first data partitioning method $z_1 = c_*$, $z_2 = u_*$, $T_{z_1} = \{\text{High } c_*, \text{Medium } c_*, \text{Low } c_*\}$, $T_{z_2} = \{\text{High } u_*, \text{Medium } u_*, \text{Low } u_*\}$, $\chi_1 = [-1.18, 0.1](\text{m/s})$, and $\chi_2 = [0.05, 0.5](\text{m/s})$. Where the values of χ_k are the entire range of c_* and u_* from Table I. The sets of membership functions $\{M_{z_1}^1, M_{z_1}^2, M_{z_1}^3\}$ and $\{M_{z_2}^1, M_{z_2}^2, M_{z_2}^3\}$ for the first partitioning method are shown in Figures 2(a) and (b) for $z_1 = c_*$ and $z_2 = u_*$, respectively. In Figures 2(a) and (b) we have chosen to use Gaussian membership functions [13] for our problem, which are defined by

$$M_{z_k}^{\ell_k}(z_k(j)) = \exp\left[-\frac{(z_k(j) - \hat{m}_{\ell_k})^2}{2\hat{\sigma}_{\ell_k}^2}\right]$$
 (8)

where \hat{m}_{ℓ_k} and $\hat{\sigma}_{\ell_k}^2$ are the estimated mean and variance respectively for the parameter of interest, computed using all training samples belonging to D_i . The membership function of (8) should not be confused with a scaled Gaussian pdf, as it is not calculating the probability or relative frequency that a measurement lies in an interval, but rather a degree of membership that a given value satisfies a fuzzy concept. As discussed in [13], there is no unique fuzzy membership function for a given problem. Besides the Gaussian there are several other common fuzzy membership functions [15], such as triangular or B-spline. Our use of the Gaussian membership function is motivated by several reasons: (1) computational tractability, (2) smooth and local behavior, and (3) the ability to assure collaboration between the different predictors in the bank by taking large values in the middle of each set, but smaller values in regions of overlap where it is hoped the different predictors will collaborate.

The confidence measure C_{ij} assigned to each predicted output \hat{y}_{ij} , based upon the degree of membership that input sample \mathbf{x}_j belongs to the i th environmentally specific data set, D_i can be determined from,

$$C_{ij} = C_{(k\ell_k)j} = M_{z_k}^{\ell_k}(z_k(j))$$
 (9)

Fig. 2. Membership functions used for the first data partitioning method based on c_* and u_* .

where j is the input sample index, in our application $k = 1, 2$ is the index of our parameter of interest (i.e. $z_1 = c_*$, $z_2 = u_*$), and $\ell_k = 1, 2, 3$ is the index of the fuzzy set (i.e. $\ell = 1, k = 1$ corresponds to the High c_* set, $\ell = 2, k = 1$ corresponds to the Medium c_* set, and so on). The membership function value $M_{z_k}^{\ell_k}(z_k(j))$ can be obtained from (8), or a different choice of membership function. For notational convenience the index i represents a relabeling of the double index $(k\ell_k)$ in (9), i.e., $i = L_k(k-1) + \ell_k$. In our application we also find it convenient to normalize the C_{ij} for a given sample j , and add a term that allows for prior weighting of each environmentally specific data subset D_i . This is done by re-defining C_{ij} as

$$C_{ij} = \frac{\alpha_i C_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^M \alpha_i C_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

where α_i is a prior weighting term added to each expert, and representing a prior knowledge that an input sample belongs to D_i , and/or that the user is more confident in the predictions from i th predictor in the bank.

The confidence measure assignment component allows prior knowledge to be incorporated into the system, and provides the ability to heavily weight conditions of interest. An example of this would be if the environmentally adaptive TL prediction system was operating in an environment where calm wind conditions were very likely to occur (low u_* values). The user would then be able to imbed a high value for α_i , corresponding to the low u_* data set. If for some reason certain predictors are known to give unreliable estimates, this information can also be imbedded into the α_i terms. For the experiments presented here we assume that all D_i are equally reliable and likely to be encountered in practice, thus $\alpha_i=1$ for all i , in our presented results.

The environmentally specific predictor outputs, \hat{y}_{ij} are multiplied by their corresponding confidence measure C_{ij} , and used to form the vector of weighted predictions $\mathbf{a}_j = [C_{1j}\hat{y}_{1j}, C_{2j}\hat{y}_{2j}, \dots, C_{Mj}\hat{y}_{Mj}]^T$. The vector \mathbf{a}_j containing the weighted estimates of the M environmentally specific predictors is then used as the input to the fusion center for sample \mathbf{x}_j .

D. Fusion Center Design

The combination rule employed by the fusion center in Figure 1 can take either a linear or non-linear approach. In each approach the vector of weighted estimates from the environmentally specific predictors, \mathbf{a}_j is used as the input to the fusion system. Assuming n available input parameter vectors in the training set, the weighted estimates of the M environmentally specific predictors are used to form the $M \times n$ matrix $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n]$. We denote the desired output vector of size $n \times 1$ as $\mathbf{d} = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n]$, and the weight vector of a linear fusion system by $\mathbf{w} = [w_1, \dots, w_M]^T$. Given the input data matrix \mathbf{A} and the desired output vector \mathbf{d} , the optimal weight vector \mathbf{w}_{opt} is obtained by solving the following least squares problem [16]:

$$\mathbf{w}_{opt} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{w}} \|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{d}\|^2 = (\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{d}. \quad (11)$$

Once found \mathbf{w}_{opt} can then be used to combine the weighted estimates from the environmentally specific predictor bank. The final output of the environmentally adaptive system in Figure 1 for the j th training sample, which is defined by \hat{y}_{TL_j} , can be obtained using, $\hat{y}_{TL_j} = \mathbf{w}_{opt}^T \mathbf{a}_j$.

A non-linear approach to our fusion problem may also be considered by using the input data matrix \mathbf{A} and desired target vector \mathbf{d} as the training data for another BPNN. For our TL prediction problem we use a BPNN of structure 6-30-1, where the six inputs correspond to the weighted estimates from the ($M=6$) environmentally specific predictors, \mathbf{a}_j . The value of the single (linear) output neuron of the fusion BPNN is then considered the final TL prediction \hat{y}_{TL_j} , and this result is compared with the PE model output to determine the error of our environmentally adaptive prediction system. Because the acoustic TL prediction problem presented in this paper is a highly non-linear regression problem, only results using the non-linear fusion scheme are presented here, as the linear fusion system was generally inadequate for our TL prediction application.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In evaluating the performance of the environmentally adaptive prediction system presented in Section III we bench-

TABLE II

RMS ERROR COMPARISON OF ENVIRONMENTALLY ADAPTIVE AND SINGLE BPNN PREDICTION METHODS ON THE PE MODEL DATA SET.

	Validation Set RMS Error (dB)	Testing Set RMS Error (dB)	$ \text{error} > 2\text{dB}$ Testing
Single BPNN	2.14	2.18	16.2%
Env. Adaptive	1.70	1.84	12.3%

mark its performance against the single BPNN prediction method discussed in [2] on the actual PE model test data. The performance measures used to evaluate TL prediction accuracy are the root mean square (RMS) error criterion, which is the standard deviation of the error (target value subtracted from BPNN prediction). The other performance measure used in our experiments is the percentage of cases where the magnitude of the error on the testing set was greater than a 2dB threshold value, i.e. the estimate generated by the prediction system is unreliable. This allows us to determine for what percentage of cases the developed predictors give inaccurate estimates. In addition to comparing the quantitative performance measures of the two methods it is also important to note the environmentally adaptive system provides the flexibility to incorporate prior knowledge into the system, and that its modular architecture can be easily modified once new conditions are encountered.

Table II gives a performance measure comparison of the environmentally adaptive and single BPNN prediction methods. As can be observed the environmentally adaptive method reduces the RMS error on the testing set by 15.6%, and reduces the percentage of cases in the testing set where the magnitude of error is greater than 2dB (outliers) by 24.1%, when compared to the single BPNN prediction method of [2]. The results lead us to state the important observation that while the environmentally adaptive system is effective in reducing the overall RMS error, it performs proportionately better on outliers when compared to the single BPNN. This reduction in the number of outliers is extremely important, as it demonstrates that the environmentally adaptive prediction system is much more likely to estimate a reliable TL value, which is within 2dB of the value calculated using the PE model.

We now examine the testing set RMS error trends as a function of the individual input parameters, which have significant influence on the TL. The binning procedure proposed in [2] is used to generate the curves plotting the RMS error as a function of individual input parameters.

Figure 3(a) shows the RMS error trend as a function of frequency, f , for the two prediction methodologies. As can be seen the RMS error values are lower for the environmentally adaptive method over the entire frequency range, and the improvements are most pronounced at high frequencies. It appears that the collaborative behavior of the environmentally adaptive system is able to better compensate for the increased refraction that occurs at high frequencies. The environmentally adaptive method also led to improvements at large values of horizontal separation between source and receiver, x_c , as shown in Figure 3(b). For the environmentally adaptive method we see a leveling off of the RMS error

curve at approximately 750m up to the maximum x_c value used in our study of 900m. The collaborative nature of the environmentally adaptive system appears able to better account for some of the PE model effects that occur at large x_c values, such as the increased likelihood of encountering refractive shadow regions where sound levels are locally depressed.

The ability of the environmentally adaptive and single BPNN predictors to approximate the non-turbulent PE model as horizontal separation, x_c , is varied, while all other input parameters are held constant is shown in Figures 4(a) and(b). For both cases of Figure 4 the single BPNN generally seems unreliable in providing an accurate approximation of the PE model. Under the baseline conditions from Table I the environmentally adaptive predictor approximates the PE model almost perfectly at a frequency of 100Hz as shown in Figure 4(a). Figure 4(b) shows the ability of the two prediction methodologies in approximating the PE model under the extreme parameter conditions from Table I at a frequency of 150Hz. The extreme parameter conditions shown in Figure 4(b), correspond to an upwind propagation direction which increases refraction, and a highly unstable atmosphere that causes sound to refract upward increasing the probability of refractive shadow regions. It is likely that these atmospheric refraction effects are responsible for the decrease in prediction accuracy at high frequencies exhibited by the neural network-based prediction systems in Figure 4(b). The main improvements of the environmentally adaptive method in Figure 4(b) appear at values of horizontal separation between 600 and 700m.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper an environmentally adaptive acoustic transmission loss prediction system was presented and developed. This environmentally adaptive system improves the accuracy of PE model approximation in terms of RMS error and number of outliers, by using a bank of expert BPNN predictors to estimate the TL. The system also exploits a decision making component to assign fuzzy confidence measures to the appropriate experts for a given input parameter combination. The decision making device also allows the user to input *a priori* information or requirements into the system, such as the likelihood and/or tactical importance of certain environmental conditions being encountered in practice. A fusion center is then used to combine the weighted estimates from the appropriate expert predictors obtaining the final TL estimate. The environmentally adaptive prediction system was tested on a synthetic PE model acoustic data set and its results were extensively benchmarked with a single BPNN predictor. The results demonstrate that the environmentally adaptive system is considerably more reliable than the single BPNN predictor, especially at high frequencies and large horizontal separation values. Future work will consist of evaluating the environmentally adaptive TL prediction system on additional acoustic data sets. Fusion schemes based on evidential theory and other data partitioning methods will also be investigated.

(a) Frequency (f)

(b) Horizontal Separation (x_c)

Fig. 3. Testing set RMS error trends for the environmentally adaptive and single BPNN predictors as a function of individual input parameters.

(a) Baseline, 100Hz

(b) Extreme, 150Hz

Fig. 4. Variation between the acoustic transmission loss as horizontal separation is varied for the PE model and two different neural network-based prediction schemes.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is supported by the DoD Center for Geosciences/Atmospheric Research at Colorado State University via Cooperative Agreement DAAD19-02-2-0005 with the Army Research Laboratory.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Srour, "Unattended ground sensors—a prospective for operational needs and requirements," ARL Technical Report prepared for NATO, October 1999.
- [2] M. Mungiole and D. K. Wilson, "Prediction of outdoor sound transmission loss with an artificial neural network," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 67, pp. 324–345, 2006.
- [3] S. Haykin, *Neural Networks: A Comprehensive Foundation, 2nd Edition*. Upper Saddle River, N.J.: Prentice Hall, 1999.
- [4] M. West, K. Gilbert, and R. A. Sack, "A tutorial on the parabolic equation (PE) model used for long range sound propagation in the atmosphere," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 37, pp. 31–49, 1992.
- [5] E. Salomons, *Computational Atmospheric Acoustics*. Norwell, MA.: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2001.
- [6] D. K. Wilson, "The sound-speed gradient and refraction in the near-ground atmosphere," *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 113, pp. 750–757, 2003.
- [7] D. K. Wilson, "Simple relaxational models for the acoustical properties of porous media," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 50, pp. 171–188, 1997.
- [8] K. Attenborough, "Acoustical impedance models for outdoor ground surfaces," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 91, pp. 521–544, 1985.
- [9] A. S. Monin and A. M. Obukhov, "Basic laws of turbulent mixing in the atmosphere near the ground," *Tr. Akad. Nauk SSR Geofiz. Inst.*, vol. 24, pp. 163–187, 1954.
- [10] T. Hastie, R. Tibshirani, and J. Friedman, *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. Springer-Verlag, 2001.
- [11] M. T. Hagan and M. B. Menhaj, "Training of feedforward networks with the Marquardt algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 113, no. 6, pp. 989–993, 1994.
- [12] L. Zadeh, "Fuzzy sets," *Information and Control*, vol. 8, pp. 338–353, 1965.
- [13] C. Harris, X. Hong, and Q. Gan, *Adaptive Modelling, Estimation and Fusion from Data*. New York: Springer-Verlag, 2002.
- [14] C. T. Lin and C. S. G. Lee, "Neural-network-based fuzzy logic control and decision system," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. 40, no. 12, pp. 1320–1336, 1991.
- [15] G. J. Klir and B. Yuan, *Fuzzy Sets and Fuzzy Logic: Theory and Applications*. Upper saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1995.
- [16] O. E. J. A. Benediktsson, J. R. Sveinsson, and P. Swain, "Parallel consensual neural network," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 8, pp. 54–64, 1997.